

MS03-2-6 TNA: Apply for access to laboratories of excellence in molecular scale biophysics research infrastructure (MOSBRI)

#MS03-2-6

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Abstract

MOSBRI provides free of charge trans-national access (TNA) to molecular-scale biophysics instrumentation and expertise, aiming at studying biological systems at an intermediate level between atomic-resolution structural descriptions and cellular-scale observations. The MOSBRI programme offers TNA to 13 European biophysical laboratories, widely distributed over Europe and selected to ensure a comprehensive portfolio of technologies and expertise. Access to the MOSBRI TNA sites is based on a proposal submitted via the MOSBRI web-site.

MOSBRI has a range of access modalities:

MOSBRI pipelines: This means an integrated access to a synergistic set of biophysical instruments and technologies. This will allow the TNA user to fully exploit the expertise of the TNA site to tackle advanced questions.

Access to instruments and methodologies: This proposal submission method may be used if you have a focused research question and already know which instrument/methodology your project needs access to.

Project maturation: If you are unsure which pipeline or instrument suite will best answer your project's scientific question, the MOSBRI's moderator panel experts can offer to guide you via project maturation.

In this poster we will present what MOSBRI TNA can offer and explain our different access modalities in detail.